

An analysis of Psycho-social elements of Hygiene with reference to the Clean India Campaign.

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Abstracts

This study aims to understand social species that create emergent organizations beyond the individual. These emergent structures evolved hand in hand with neural, hormonal, cellular, and genetic mechanisms to support them because the consequent social behaviors helped these organisms survive, reproduce, and care for offspring sufficiently long that they too reproduced. Social neuroscience seeks to specify the neural, hormonal, cellular, and genetic mechanisms underlying social behavior, and in so doing to understand the associations and influences between social and biological levels of organization. Success in the field, therefore, is not measured in terms of the contributions to social psychology per se, but rather in terms of the specification of the biological mechanisms underlying social interactions and behavior—one of the major problems for the neurosciences to address in the 21st century. (Cacioppo, J. T., Berntson, G. G., & Decety, J. (2010).

It also aims at implementation Swachh Bharat Mission-Gramin campaign in India and investigate the available literature regarding claim of the 100% open defecation free status and complete management of solid and liquid waste management. This research used qualitative method using various reports and data to verify the claim by Government of India. The purpose for this study is to assist policymaker with more relevant data and fact pertaining to ODF status and viability of utilities for better waste management processes at rural level. This examine seems on the view of understudies which can be reflecting the validate data's and reports on accurate There was a gap between the impressions of the government claims and report and studies conducted by some independent agencies. This examine intends to recognize whether the potential to cope-up with current policy framework and efforts to uplift current situation at rural area.

Keywords: 1. Comptroller and Auditor General of India, 2. Community Led Total Sanitation, 3. Information, Education, Communication. 4. Social neuroscience, 5. Swachh Bharat Mission-Gramin, 6. Solid & Liquid Waste Management, 7. Open Defecation Free.

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1. Introduction

Every year 525,000 children die due to diarrhea out of the 1.7 billion cases of childhood diarrhea worldwide(WHO, 2018) Swachh Bharat Mission" (SBM) (Clean India Mission) is India's biggest ever cleanliness drive which was launched in October 2, 2014, with the objective of having clean and hygienic India so that every Indian citizen can have access to healthy and hygienic facilities such as household sanitary latrines, community latrines, proper waste disposal system, cleanliness drive up to village level, and ensuring safe drinking water supply

to every house. The mission has two sub-missions, the SBM (Gramin) and the SBM (Urban), which aim to achieve Swachh Bharat by 2019, as a fitting tribute to the 150th Birth Anniversary of Mahatma Gandhi. Improving the access to safe drinking water and adequate sanitation, as well as promoting good hygiene, are key components. A report by the World Health Organization in collaboration with the UNICEF indicated that in 2006, an estimated 2.5 billion people were lacking improved sanitation facilities. Moreover, nearly one in four people in developing countries were practicing open

defecation. The Millennium Development Goal number 7, for 2015, is aimed at reducing the proportion of people without sustainable access to safe drinking water and basic sanitation facilities by half, focusing mostly on the provision of infrastructure to meet the demands of communities in developing countries. Poor sanitation is responsible for 10% of the global disease burden, causing diarrheal diseases, neglected tropical diseases, acute respiratory diseases and malnutrition among children (Mara D. 2017)

2. Review of Literature

People were compelled to go for open defecation due to not having a latrine at home or having a latrine structure that was used for alternate purposes (e.g. storing grains). Other reasons compelling open defecation are the fear that latrine would get dirty quicker, the latrine is for used only for guests, or on certain occasions or time of the day; and the existing cultural norms of not sharing latrines between male and female members. People with access to public latrines were still compelled to go out for defecation due to the issues related to long queuing, hygiene issues as the public latrines are usually dirty and the cultural norms of latrine sharing restriction between male and female members of the society. Additionally, females also reported that they did not want to be seen by the male members while queuing in public latrines, which compelled them to go out in the open spaces for defecation. The research highlights a prominent gender component related to the practice of open defecation. The propriety still dictates that women and girls are still not considered of their opinion or needs for sanitary practices. Women and girls are compelled to go for open defecation either due to the absence of a latrine at home or they are not allowed to use the latrine at home as it to be used by the male members of the family. Women and girls also fear harassment or have privacy issues of being seen by the men from the community both during public latrine use and on the way to open defecation.(Bhatt, 2019)

In India, approximately 53% of households and 624 million people defecate in the open area. Open defecation is more pervasive in rural versus urban areas (74% vs. 17%). Knowledge, attitude, and practice studies are very important in community level assessment of an ongoing health program. In the above scenario, the present study was aimed at assessing the knowledge and practices regarding water, sanitation hygiene, and waste disposal and the key components of SBM or Swachh Bharat Abhiyan (SBA) (Anjan Datta Et.al., 2021).

Social neuroscience is also grounded in the premise that there are lawful relationships among biological, psychological, and social processes. This notion dates back at least to the third century B.C.E., when the Greek physician Erasistratos used his observations of peripheral physiological responses, such as the appearance of an irregular heartbeat and pallor in a young man when his stepmother visited, to identify the cause of the individual's malady— lovesickness (Mesulam & Perry, 1972).

Basic sanitation facilities are accessible to only 68% of the global population. Among 2.3 billion people who lack access to toilets or latrines, 892 million still defecate in the open places. Higher under-five mortality and malnutrition rates are reported in countries which have higher proportions of people practicing open field defecation. Open defecation is also associated with violence against women in the low middle-income countries (LMIC) including rape among women and girls. (Clair RP, 2018)

During much of the 20th century in the neurosciences, the individual was treated as the fundamental unit of analysis, and the brain was treated as a solitary information-processing organ. This is an entirely understandable starting point. The brain, the organ of the mind, is housed deep within the cranial vault, where it is protected and isolated from others, as are the neural, hormonal, and genetic processes of interest to most biological

scientists. Even cognition, emotion, and behavior can be thought of as beginning with the neurobiological events within individual organisms, events that can be isolated and examined. It should be no surprise, therefore, that the study of human behavior by neuroscientists, and many cognitive and behavioral scientists, in the 20th century tended to focus on single organisms, organs, cells, intracellular processes, and genes. (Cacioppo, et.al, 2010).

Human social behavior is complex, and many behaviors can be ambiguous as to their origins. One may eat because one is hungry, but often it is a habit to eat at a particular time of day, or a social occasion in which the consumption of food is the norm. The identification of which genes, gene transcripts, proteins, cells, cell assemblies, brain regions, and neural networks are relevant to a given behavior is advanced by the empirical isolation of the underlying psychological component processes. Social psychology is rich in theoretical models that specify conceptual structures and processes underlying a variety of social behaviors, and behavioral paradigms exist that permit the isolation of posited structures and processes for empirical analysis. These theoretical specifications and paradigms are important for understanding the biological bases of social psychological and behavioral processes because the brain and genes are sufficiently complex that the identification of their operation is likely to be fostered by theories of the mind and behavior to guide the process of empirical exploration and discovery.

The flagship program Launched by the Prime Minister in August 2014, the Swachh Bharat Mission (SBM) has been progressing at a rapid pace. Individual household latrine (IHHL) construction has accelerated, with estimates projecting 75-85 per cent coverage by October 2019. As a result, lakhs of villages and hundreds of districts have been declared open defecation free (ODF) across the country. However, state that despite an increased policy

focus on toilet usage and strong promotion of community led total sanitation (CLTS) methods, in many parts of the country, the SBM is implemented in a construction-focused and target-driven mode, which often leads to perverse incentives. Over 90 per cent of the total SBM expenditure goes to toilet construction, at the expense of allocations for information, education and communication (IEC). Actual expenditure is even lower: only 1 per cent of the total IEC allocation was spent in 2015-16. The quality of implementation of behavior change approaches like CLTS tends to be poor and there is evidence that suggests gaps in behaviour change, with households gaining access to toilets not necessarily using them or using them sporadically. The aim of our research was to understand and review successful practices in approaches to behavior change in districts declared ODF by the Government. It unpacks what approaches have proven effective in motivating collective behavior change at scale in rural India and seeks to understand how and why these changes have taken place.

3. Methodology

This study is purely based on secondary data wherein researchers have tried to describe the concern in systematic and appropriate manner. For the same guidelines and reports on related topic have been studied.

3.1 Significance of the Study:-

Since SBM-G is flagship program of government of India to eradicate open defecation and promoting safe sanitation to citizens. SBM-G is one of the programmes supported by World Bank and other funding agencies for promoting proper infrastructure and strengthening existing sanitation policies in India.

As Government is taking initiatives for safe and healthy environment for Indian citizens by launching this very nature of programmes, it is imperative to observe the implementation and execution. It is also

important to probe and evaluate the accountability and financial mechanism as well.

Hence, researchers developed the keen interest to compare and analyze the financial aspect on the impact and effectiveness of SBM-G.

3.2 Objectives:

- To evaluate the Psychological element of hygiene
- To understand the policy measures to control the behavioral patterns of rural People
- To evaluate the social and psychological relationship of prioritizing hygiene in daily lives.
- To analyze the effectiveness & impact of Programme.

3.3 Scope of the study:

The conclusions derived from the study focuses on various publications, reports with reference to maintaining hygiene and other mentioned policy measures in the state of India and financial allotment and its utilizations for various purposes. This study will be helpful in understanding the outcomes and suggest possible interventions for effective execution.

4 Data Analysis:

To analyze & reach to the conclusion, researchers have referred various articles and reports related to behavioral patterns and Secondary data have been utilized for analysis.

1. The Comptroller and Auditor General (CAG) has said that the government's claim of Gujarat being 'Open Defecation Free'(ODF) appears to be wrong, as many rural households were found to have no toilets. In a survey conducted in eight districts, nearly 30 per cent of houses were found to have no toilets, said the CAG report tabled in the state Assembly on Wednesday (September 19). The Union government

had informed the Lok Sabha in February this year that 11 states including Gujarat have been declared as ODF under the Swachh Bharat Mission (SBM).

The survey was conducted in the districts of Dahod, Banaskantha, Chhotaudepur, Dang, Patan, Valsad, Jamnagar and Junagadh. Of the total of 54,008 households in eight districts, 15,728 households had no access to toilets, the CAG said. "Audit observed that the administration had declared all the districts as ODF on achieving the targets set out in the baseline survey conducted in 2012," noted the CAG. "However, this list was not updated after 2012 and therefore, a number of households did not have any access to toilets and they remained uncovered," said the report.

When the issue was raised with the state government in March 2018, the authorities claimed that all the villages are now ODF, as more toilets were built later "through CSR (corporate social responsibility) initiative". However, the CAG noted, auditors observed that people were still not able to use toilets due to various reasons. In 41 out of the total 120 test-checked villages, the toilets constructed under the Swachh Bharat Mission could not be used as there was no water connection, it said. In 15 villages "toilets were not being used either due to non-availability of water and soak pits or they were incomplete", the report said. In tribal-dominated Kaprada block of Valsad district, over 17,400 toilets were found to be "defunct", it said (Press Trust of India 2018).

2. The United Nations calls for eliminating open defecation by 2025. Open defecation has been incorporated in the Sustainable Development Goals (SDG) in target 6.2 aiming to "achieve

access to adequate and equitable sanitation and hygiene for all and end open defecation, paying special attention to the needs of women and girls and those in vulnerable situations by 2030" (United Nations, 2018)

3. Among the world's population who practice open defecation, more than two-thirds (558 million) live in the rural areas of South Asia. With continuous efforts, the proportion of people practicing open defecation in South Asia dropped from 65% in 1990 to 34% in 2018. Despite the efforts through different approaches, attaining and sustaining the 'open defecation free' status has been possible only in less than half of the places globally. The available quantitative data on open defecation provides limited information regarding the motivations for open defecation. A qualitative study from Zambia suggests that the preference for defecation practice of either using a latrine or going for open defecation may have deep-rooted cultural influences. (Thys S, 2015)
4. India is a low-income country in South Asia with a population of 28 million with 83% of the population residing in the rural areas and one-fourth of the population living below the poverty line. As per the 2016 India Demographic Health Survey (NDHS), the under-five mortality and infant mortality rates are 39 and 32 deaths per 1000 live births respectively with diarrhea as the major cause of childhood morbidity and mortality in India. According to NDHS 2016, 62% of the households in India have access to an improved sanitation facility, 22% people have access to shared facilities, 1.6% have access to unimproved facilities and about 15% have no facility thus use open space for defecation. Improved sanitation facilities include

any non-shared toilet of the following types: flush/pour flush toilets to piped sewer systems, septic tanks, and pit latrines; ventilated improved pit (VIP) latrines; pit latrines with slabs; and composting toilets. Unimproved facilities include shared toilets that are used by more than 2 households or flush/pour toilets that are not connected to piped sewers, septic tanks and open pit latrines. The proportion of open defecation practice is higher in rural areas than in urban areas (21% vs. 11%). Open spaces for defecation include behind the bushes, open fields and the river banks. Inadequate sanitation is a major factor responsible for diarrhea cases in children in India. (Budhathoki SS,, 2016).

5. Government and non-government agencies began efforts to increase latrine coverage in India since 1990, followed by CLTS in 2003 and SLTS in 2006. The latter approaches emphasized on creating open defecation free (ODF) communities in Nepal. Nepal Government emphasizes that 'Open defecation free' area is an area with no feces exposed to air. Thereby an 'ODF' status is given to an area if there is no open defecation in the designated area at any given time; all households have access to improved sanitation facilities (toilets) with full use, operation, and maintenance; and all the schools, institutions or offices within the designated areas have toilet facilities (Sahoo KC, 2015).

5 Conclusion

Open defecation is chosen willingly or by compulsion by people in the communities. Understanding the personal preferences, perceptions, religious beliefs, family/cultural norms, societal practices, and availability of resources may help design better interventions

for alleviating the practice of open defecation. There is a need to give careful considerations for understanding the motivations among females for open defecation in order to address open defecation and promote latrine use in a more gender equitable manner. Cleanliness is dream of every citizen and somehow defines our images on global platforms. Unhygienic places to live leads to poor health and poor health are major determinants for low level economic standards. Comparison of Several data with other data is not to challenge the Positive outcomes but to support and up lift the poor part for improvement for actual realization of fact and sense of supporting system for policy maker to take more precise decision.

SBM-G has brought in a remarkable impact and providing benefits to the society at large. It is one of the largest cleanliness drives in the world in terms of Funds and Coverage. It has been reported than till today 9.5 core toilets has been built in India which is huge success for any nation but simultaneously some reports are totally contradict to such fact. Denial of such fact has big question for society too. Construction of toilet is not only the solution but must be monitored regularly whether these are being used by the people at large or not, people are made aware about the importance of using the same and the allied resources are also to be provided with for proper use of toilets under implementation aspect of SBM-G scheme.

Through this present study researchers have tried to touch upon the implementation aspect of allocated fund under SBM-G and its impact on beneficiaries from the state of Gujarat.

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